

An Integrated Participatory Design Process to Define Intervention Strategies and Technological Tools for the Prevention of Overweight/Obesity

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ABSTRACT

Being overweight or obese raises the chances of developing a number of illnesses. Maintaining a healthy weight can help avoid these health problems, halt their progression, or resolve them. A variety of intervention strategies and digital tools have been implemented for obesity prevention. However, these strategies and tools often are not designed in consideration of the end users' needs and preferences. To overcome this limitation, the study proposes an integrated participatory design process based on the design thinking and user-centered design methods, which involves end-users and the wider community in a synergistic dialogue. This dialogue can help define intervention strategies and technological tools for obesity prevention.

KEYWORDS

Co-Creation, Design Thinking, Healthy Lifestyle, Obesity, Overweight, Participatory Design, Prevention Strategies, User-Centred Design

INTRODUCTION

A person is determined to be overweight or obese when their body weight is above what is considered healthy for their height (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020). These conditions represent major public health concerns as they are associated with additional health risks, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and other metabolic conditions (J. S. Wang et al., 2023). Several intervention strategies have been implemented for obesity prevention, including policy interventions and community-based interventions (Barquera & Seidell, 2021). In addition, the introduction of new digital technologies has tremendous potential for impacting lifestyle choices and health, providing viable and personalized well-being services to meet individualized needs (Garcia et al., 2022; Kolasa & Kozinski, 2020; Labrique et al., 2020).

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However, a top-down approach without the involvement of the user has dominated most of the prevention strategies, resulting in their limited success (McGlashan et al., 2018; Roberto et al., 2015). In addition, in most cases, the digital tools used are not intuitive and easy to use, they may require time-consuming food logging/monitoring, they focus on interventions either via diet or physical activity, and they fail to engage over the long-term.

All of these problems could be overcome by following a bottom-up approach in the design, implementation, and evaluation of the intervention strategies and technological tools; this implies the involvement of the end-users and a wide variety of stakeholders in a synergistic dialogue to co-define multi-modal intervention measures (Willmott et al., 2022).

The involvement of end-users and the wider community can be achieved using a participatory design process that allows stakeholders to express their concerns and provide ideas and suggestions for promoting successful, user-friendly solutions (D'Andrea & D'Ulizia, 2023, 2024; D'Andrea et al., 2015, 2025; Ferri et al., 2020; Loewenson et al., 2014).

The research question guiding this study is: How do we design intervention strategies and healthy lifestyle technological tools for obesity prevention using a participatory process?

This paper aims to answer this research question by exploring the potential of an integrated participatory design process (IPDP) combining two participatory methodologies, namely design thinking (DT) and user-centered design (UCD), to simultaneously investigate the design process from two perspectives: first, at the strategic level; and second, at the technological level. This approach has the benefit that the technological tools are designed in the larger context of the healthcare system rather than as standalone solutions. This IPDP allows for stimulating the engagement of end users and different kinds of stakeholders; the aim is the co-creation of intervention strategies and the co-design of technological tools for obesity prevention.

The proposed IPDP will be implemented within the HealthyW8 project (<https://www.healthyw8.eu/>) funded by the European Commission under the Horizon program. HealthyW8 aims to step up primary obesity prevention efforts across Europe, endowing them with a multi-disciplinary portfolio approach that combines a large set of interventions and implementation options, based mainly on a healthy lifestyle recommender solution and a human digital twin. The conception of the participatory design process followed to co-define the set of intervention strategies and the functionalities of the healthy lifestyle recommender solution and healthy digital twin is illustrated in this paper. In particular, two well-synchronized cycles have been defined to collect experiences, motivations, and needs regarding intervention strategies and user requirements—as well as to discuss, identify, and prioritize intervention strategies and desired tools' functionalities for the HealthyW8 portfolio.

The paper is structured as follows. The second section provides certain concepts and notions of participatory design in the field of obesity prevention, while in the third section the proposed IPDP is described. The fourth section illustrates the implementation of the IPDP within the HealthyW8 project, and in the fifth section, the results from a pre-validation of the IPDP are provided. Finally, the last section concludes the paper.

BACKGROUND

Over the past 40 years, the prevalence of obesity has tripled worldwide. Indeed, 13% of adults globally are obese, and 40% of adults globally are overweight (World Health Organization, 2018). Obesity can shorten life expectancy, increase the risk of numerous co-morbidities, and raise mortality rates. According to data from the 2015 Global Burden of Disease, having a high BMI was associated with an additional mortality of 7% from all causes (Afshin et al., 2017).

From an economic and social perspective, the prevention of obesity makes more sense than treatment options. Lifestyle interventions that promote healthy eating and physical activity are the cornerstones of obesity prevention in adults and adolescents. However, these interventions have had only a modest impact on reducing obesity and obesity-related behaviors due to the nature of

face-to-face interventions that limit participation and the ability to impose healthy behavior changes that last (Tully et al., 2020; Y. Wang et al., 2015). The use of digital devices has been proposed as a potential strategy for overcoming these limitations (Laing et al., 2018), which would contribute to decreasing the rates of obesity (Byambasuren et al., 2018; Castelnuovo et al., 2014). Technology-based interventions use digital devices to deliver personalized and real-time health promotions and disease prevention interventions (Chow et al., 2015; Michie et al., 2017; Redfern et al., 2016). Three recent systematic reviews concluded that technology-supported intervention strategies can be effective in managing weight loss in patients with obesity (Kouvari et al., 2022; Raaijmakers et al., 2015; Rumbo-Rodríguez et al., 2020).

Moreover, recent studies emphasize engaging different stakeholders, including end users, in designing, implementing, and evaluating obesity prevention strategies supported by technological tools (Partridge & Redfern, 2018; Willmott et al., 2022) using a participatory process (Gokee-LaRose et al., 2009).

In this perspective, this paper provides an IPDP for defining intervention strategies in the public health sector. Starting from the definition of a co-design process proposed by Jones et al. (2020), the IPDP is defined as a process of collective creativity or partnership with potential users and stakeholders, who are actively involved in the ideation of intervention strategies and the development of healthy lifestyle technological tools.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, a detailed description of the IPDP is provided. The proposed IPDP aims to: engage end users and stakeholders in highly participatory debates, consultation, and co-design activities; integrate all end users and stakeholders' visions, needs, and desires into the design of intervention strategies; and apply inclusive mechanisms for sharing knowledge, building mutual understanding, and co-designing solutions to obesity prevention and management.

The IPDP integrates two participatory methodologies:

1. **DT:** This is a method of problem-solving that incorporates experimentation, empathy, and iteration. This approach promotes unconventional thinking and views issues from several angles to find creative solutions. It is composed of five stages, as proposed by the Hasso-Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford (Plattner, 2013). These phases may be cyclical or linear, based on the needs of the project.
2. **UCD:** This design methodology aims to develop solutions that, while taking into account users' needs, wants, and limitations, provide users with relevant and meaningful experiences. Comprehensive user research, user case development, and ongoing integration of direct user feedback into the solution are all phases of UCD methodology. It guarantees that users may quickly become accustomed to new software, minimize errors, and boost output. This methodology is composed of three stages, as proposed by Lowdermilk (2013). Figure 1 shows the IPDP as defined within the HealthyW8 project.

Figure 1. The integrated participatory design process (IPDP) defined and planned within the HealthyW8 project

For choosing the methodologies to use within the participatory process, the benefits and disadvantages of suitable participatory research approaches and frameworks have been analyzed (Ferri et al., 2020). DT and UCD were judged to be the most suitable for the development of simple, user-friendly solutions to fight against obesity. In fact, too often obesity interventions have been designed based on what clinicians think (Graham et al., 2021), leading to users not wanting to use the interventions. To rectify these problems, UCD and DT have been selected. With their foundations in human-centric concepts, these two methodologies allow one to design obesity intervention strategies and tools tailored to the users' requirements and needs. Although they are both human-centric, UCD and DT use different approaches and have different uses. UCD places greater emphasis on designing technological tools' functionalities, ensuring that they are customized to the needs and skills of the user. On the other hand, DT promotes designing "with the user" strategies and/or policies strongly focused on innovation by prioritizing understanding of the user's problem within a wider context and taking into account a variety of potential outcomes to redefine challenges, question presumptions, and come up with creative solutions.

Using a blended design approach harnesses the strengths of each, leading to innovative and highly usable obesity and overweight intervention strategies and tools. This blended approach exploits the UCD's emphasis on in-depth user research and understanding of user needs, wants, and limitations by enabling developers to design solutions tailored to the user's requirements. Integrating DT expands this process by encouraging a divergent, creative, ideation phase to generate a multitude of potential solutions.

The HealthyW8 project implements the IPDP with two well-synchronized cycles of stakeholder workshops and field trials, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The two cycles of the integrated participatory design process (IPDP)

The first cycle consists of two rounds of nine participatory local workshops in which the targeted end users (primary schoolchildren with active parent involvement), young adults (18–25 years), and the elderly (>65years) and different categories of stakeholders are involved. These workshops are organized at the local level in the nine countries involved in the HealthyW8 project (Italy, Romania, Luxemburg, Bulgaria, Portugal, Germany, Spain, the Netherlands, and Denmark).

In the first round, both the empathize and define phases of the DT strategy and the understanding phase of the UCD approach are implemented. The goal is to proactively engage actors to better understand their experiences, motivations, and needs about the intervention strategies.

In the second round, the ideate and prototype phases of the DT strategy and the conceptualization phase of the UCD approach are performed. The goal is to engage participants in discussing, identifying, and prioritizing intervention strategies and to come out with ideas on desired functionalities that are perceived as being useful and relevant for the design and development of the HealthyW8 portfolio of tools.

The first cycle ends with the testing phase that involves the short pilot trials (<3 months). The goal is to validate the most relevant intervention strategies and functionalities of the tools that emerged during the previous phases.

The second cycle of the IPDP consists of one round of international participatory workshops organized online using a co-creation, one for each target group addressed in the project. In this round, the ideate and prototype phases of the DT strategy and the conceptualization phase of the UCD approach are performed again. The goal is to gather further ideas from many geographically dispersed stakeholders to optimize the set of intervention strategies.

The second cycle ends with the testing phase that is carried out in the long intervention trials. As for the short trial, the aim is to validate the most relevant intervention strategies and functionalities of the tools that emerged during the previous phases.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE IPDP

In this section, a detailed description of the two cycles of the IPDP applied to the HealthyW8 project is provided.

The First Cycle of the IPDP

As described previously, the first cycle of the IPDP consists of two rounds of participatory design workshops organized in nine countries involved in the HealthyW8 project. Figure 3 shows the outcomes expected by the implementation of the different stages of the IPDP.

Figure 3. The first cycle of the integrated participatory design process (IPDP)

The following sub-sections provide a detailed description of the activities performed during the first and second rounds of the first cycle of the IPDP.

The First Round

In the first round, relevant actors are engaged to better understand their experiences, motivations, and needs about the intervention strategies and to collect user requirements to configure the tools in the HealthyW8 portfolio.

For the collection of experiences, motivations, and needs about the intervention strategies for promoting healthy lifestyles, participants are asked to write a description on: experiences related to eating habits and behaviors of a healthy lifestyle; difficulties in adopting eating habits and behaviors for a healthy lifestyle; and needs to overcome difficulties in adopting eating habits and behaviors for a healthy lifestyle.

According to the category to which participants belong, they are asked to answer the triggering questions illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Triggering questions for the collection of experiences, motivations, and needs

Participants Category	Triggering Questions
- Young adults (18–25 years) - Elderly (>65 years) - Citizens/society at large	1) Can you tell us about your eating habits and the behaviors you adopt to lead a healthy lifestyle? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties you encounter in your eating habits and in behaviors you adopt to lead a healthy lifestyle? 3) Can you tell us about what you need to overcome the difficulties encountered in adopting eating habits and behaviors to lead a healthy lifestyle?
- Parents of primary schoolchildren	1) Can you tell us about the eating habits and behaviors adopted by your sons and/or daughters to lead a healthy lifestyle? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties that your sons and/or daughters encounter in their eating habits and behaviors in leading a healthy lifestyle? 3) Can you tell us about what your sons and/or daughters need to overcome the difficulties encountered in adopting eating habits and behaviors to lead a healthy lifestyle?
- Healthcare professionals - Educators - Health care services - Food industries and wholesalers - Sport organizations - Insurance companies	1) Can you tell us about the eating habits and behaviors of your patients/students/members? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties that your patients/students/organization members encounter? 3) Can you tell us about what your patients/students/members need to overcome the difficulties encountered in adopting eating habits and behaviors that lead to a healthy lifestyle?

Participants share the descriptions with others to emphasize and create a mutual understanding of their different points of view. Several heterogeneous groups of participants are then formed.

Participants at each table are invited to analyze and discuss a list of existing intervention strategies, to discuss further strategies, and to propose ideas that answer the three following triggering questions:

1. Which of the existing intervention strategies do you think can contribute most to stimulating a healthy lifestyle? Why?
2. What further intervention strategies do you know that were not mentioned in the list you have been provided?
3. What innovative solutions should be implemented to improve the effectiveness of existing intervention strategies to promote a healthy lifestyle?

Finally, the last triggering question participants are asked to vote on the two most relevant solutions.

To identify the functionalities that should be configured in the digital tools of the HealthyW8 portfolio, participants are asked to describe: experience in using digital tools that help to lead a healthy lifestyle; difficulties encountered in using these digital tools to lead a healthy lifestyle; and benefits of using these digital tools to lead a healthy lifestyle.

According to the category to which participants belong, they are asked to answer the triggering questions, as illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Triggering questions for the collection of the user requirements

Participants Category	Triggering Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young adults (18–25 years) - Elderly (>65 years) - Citizens/society at large 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Can you tell us about your experience in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties you encounter in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 3) Can you tell us about what you need to overcome the difficulties encountered in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parents of primary schoolchildren 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Can you tell us about your sons' and/or daughters' experience in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties that your sons and/or daughters encounter in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 3) Can you tell us about what your sons and/or daughters need to overcome the difficulties encountered in using technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Healthcare professionals - Educators - Health care services - Food industries and wholesalers - Sport organizations - Insurance companies 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Can you tell us about the experience of your patients/students/organization members in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 2) Can you tell us about the difficulties your patients/students/organization members face in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 3) Can you tell us about what your patients/students/organization members need to overcome the difficulties they face in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy-makers and government authorities - Academic/scientific communities 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Based on your experience/studies conducted, can you tell us about the digital technological tools that are most used by the reference population? 2) Based on your experience/studies conducted, can you tell us about the difficulties that the reference population encounters in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle? 3) Based on your experience/studies conducted, can you tell us about what the reference population needs to overcome the difficulties encountered in using digital technological tools to lead a healthy lifestyle?

Participants share the descriptions with the other participants to create a mutual understanding of the different points of view. Different heterogeneous groups of participants are then formed. Videos illustrating the functionalities of the existing digital tools previously developed by the partners of the HealthyW8 project (Van Gorp & Nuijten, 2023) are shown to participants of each table, who are invited to discuss and propose ideas that answer the three following triggering questions:

1. Which of the existing digital tools do you think contribute the most to stimulating a healthy lifestyle? Why?
2. Which are the functionalities of digital tools shown in the videos that better help to change behavior toward more healthy lifestyles?
3. Which new functionalities of the digital tools do you suggest to implement for stimulating a healthy lifestyle?

Finally, considering the last triggering question, participants are asked to vote on the two most relevant solutions.

The Second Round

In the second round, participants are engaged in discussing, identifying, and prioritizing intervention strategies and coming out with ideas on desired functionalities perceived as being useful and relevant for the design and development of the HealthyW8 portfolio of tools.

For the discussion, identification, and prioritization of intervention strategies, several heterogeneous groups of participants are formed. Participants of each table are invited to discuss the pros and cons of the most voted for innovative intervention strategies resulting from the first round of local workshops organized in each country. Moreover, participants of each table are invited to discuss how to implement the two most voted for innovative intervention strategies by answering the following triggering questions:

1. Which actors do you think have to be involved in implementing the intervention strategy?
2. Which technological tool(s) can support the implementation of the intervention strategy? How?
3. Does the intervention strategy need to be personalized according to the features of the user? If yes, how do you suggest personalizing it?

For the ideation of the desired functionalities of the HealthyW8 portfolio of tools, participants are invited to discuss personas that might use the HealthyW8 portfolio of tools. Cooper (1999) defined personas as a UCD and human-computer interaction technique that promotes immersion into end-users' needs.

To have a better understanding of the most important target users and stakeholders that interact with the technological tools, a draft description of several personas provided by the organizers of the short trials is shown to participants.

Each participant is invited to read the description of the personas and write possible suggestions and improvements.

Moreover, to allow participants to contribute to the conceptualization of the most voted for functionalities of the technological tools the mock-up design method is used (Interaction Design Foundation, 2015). Specifically, the technological partners of the HealthyW8 project chose the Figma tool, which provides an online collaborative editor supporting a set of common widgets for mobile applications for realistic screen designs. To prepare for the workshop, the partners first imported the screens of their existing applications into Figma sheets and then remixed them as interactive high-fidelity prototypes that illustrate some implementation of the most voted for functionalities that emerged from the first round of workshops.

Heterogeneous groups of participants are formed and invited to discuss how to improve the provided mock-ups. Instead of using Figma, they receive paper handouts with sequences of screen designs, as seen in Figure 4, to add their comments regarding the following questions:

1. Does the mock-up conceptualize the suggested functionality? If not, how do you suggest improving it?
2. Considering the flow and sequencing of the frames, is it coherent and intuitive? How do you suggest improving it?
3. Considering the textual content of each frame, is it clear? How do you suggest improving it?
4. Considering the graphics of each frame, is it appropriate? How do you suggest improving it?

Figure 4. Example of handouts with sequences of screen designs

We also provide a template with a sequence of empty smartphone screens to the stakeholders to let them sketch their ideas. Figure 5 shows the template.

Figure 5. Template with a sequence of empty smartphone screens

Testing in Short Pilot Trials

The testing phase of the selected tool-assisted intervention strategies occurs during the short pilot trials that have a maximum duration of three months. The goal is to validate the most relevant intervention strategies and functionalities of the tools that emerged during the previous phases among different end-user groups within different contexts. The assessment of their efficacy—considering psychological/emotional states, adherence to dietary suggestions, technology acceptance, efficacy of nudges, user-friendliness of the tools, and actual usage and engagement—is performed.

The Second Cycle of the IPDP

Starting from the feedback received from the testing in short pilot trials, the second cycle of the IPDP is implemented. Figure 6 shows the outcomes expected by the implementation of the different stages of the IPDP.

Figure 6. The second cycle of the integrated participatory design process (IPDP)

It consists of one round of international participatory workshops organized online using a co-creation platform, one for each target group addressed in the project. In this round, three representatives of stakeholders participating in each local workshop organized in the first cycle are engaged to gather further ideas from many geographically dispersed stakeholders for optimizing the set of intervention strategies.

To gather ideas for optimizing the set of intervention strategies, for each online workshop the list of the intervention strategies validated during the trials involving each target group as well as the emerged critical/negative aspects are shown to participants. Several heterogeneous groups of participants are formed within the online co-creation platform. Participants in each online room are invited to discuss the critical/negative aspects that emerged from the validation and to ideate possible refinement by answering the following triggering questions:

1. Considering the critical aspects that emerged from the feedback of the pilot trials, which changes to the intervention strategy do you suggest overcoming the critical aspects?
2. Considering the critical aspects that emerged from the feedback of the pilot trials, if the intervention strategy envisages the use of technological tool(s) for its implementation, which changes to the tools' functionalities do you suggest overcoming the critical aspects?

For the refinement of the functionalities of the HealthyW8 portfolio of tools, participants are invited to discuss how to improve the description of the personas related to the target group addressed in the workshop according to the feedback of the short trials. Specifically, participants in each online room are invited to read the description of the personas and write possible suggestions and improvements.

Moreover, to allow participants to contribute to the refinement of the functionalities of the technological tools, the technological partners of the HealthyW8 project developed the prototypes of the technological tools with the most voted for functionalities.

Heterogeneous groups of participants are formed and invited to use the prototypes and discuss how to improve them by answering the following questions:

1. Do the prototypes conceptualize the suggested functionality? If not, how do you suggest improving them?
2. Considering the flow and sequencing of the interfaces, is it coherent and intuitive? How do you suggest improving it?
3. Considering the textual content of the interface, is it clear? How do you suggest improving it?
4. Considering the graphics design of the interface, is it appropriate? How do you suggest improving it?

Testing in Long Trials

The testing phase of the optimized intervention strategies and refined tools' functionalities occurs during the long intervention trials, which have a duration of one year. The goal is to assess if the intervention strategies and the use of the refined tools' functionalities allow reducing the risk of obesity at various life stages in different end-user groups within different contexts.

Pre-Validation of the IPDP

The proposed IPDP will be applied in the next months within the HealthyW8 project. To obtain preliminary feedback, a pre-validation was conducted before proceeding to the implementation of the IPDP and its formal validation.

This section presents the results obtained from the pre-validation and the lessons learned.

A short questionnaire has been formulated to measure the extent to which end users and stakeholders participating in the IPDP agreed that the stages of the IPDP successfully enable the achievement of the HealthyW8 objectives of iteratively developing and optimizing user-centered portfolio intervention strategies. The questionnaire, designed to take less than 10 minutes to complete, consists of a series of nine questions mainly related to: the adequacy of the IPDP for the intended purpose; the achievement of the IPDP objectives; the understandability and clarity of the activities to be performed; and the reusability of the results and knowledge produced during the process. The questionnaire is shown in the Appendix.

Thirteen stakeholders filled in the questionnaire. They were selected in Italy and belong to the following main areas of practice: healthcare professionals, food experts, academics, teachers, parents of primary schoolchildren, elderly persons, and citizens. We chose to involve only Italian stakeholders in the pre-validation because the first participatory local workshops are planned in Italy. As the participatory local workshops planned during the first cycle of the IPDP are carried out, all the stakeholders from the nine countries that are part of the HealthyW8 consortium will be involved in the formal validation.

Stakeholders were trained with the aim and scope of the HealthyW8 project and with the steps and planned activities of the IPDP by also providing a simulation of the planned process. Afterward, the questionnaire in the Appendix was administered to them.

The results achieved from the questionnaire were very encouraging: most of the stakeholders appreciated the participative experience that they considered adequate to outline innovative intervention strategies and tools' functionalities for obesity prevention and healthy lifestyle stimulation. The planned objectives could be achieved by most of the participants, while one stakeholder (7.7%) judged the objectives' achievement and the other ones suggested to include a discussion about the feedback received by stakeholders. All of the stakeholders perceived the activities planned in the IPDP to be understandable. Lastly, the stakeholders' opinion regarding the reusability of the produced knowledge and results of the process was not positive. Most of the stakeholders abstained from answering the question regarding the reusability of the results, followed by four stakeholders

answering positively and one stakeholder negatively. The application in the workplace was indicated by stakeholders as the main area of reusability of the results.

Table 3. Preliminary validation questions

Topics	Percentage of Positive Answers	Percentage of Negative Answers	Percentage of Abstaining/Neutral Answers	Lessons Learned From Stakeholders
Adequacy of the process to identify innovative intervention strategies and tools' functionalities	92.3%	0%	7.7%	The duration of the activities planned in the process should be increased to allow more in-depth discussion
Understandability of the questions and activities planned in the process	100%	0%	0%	
Achievement of planned objectives	69.2%	7.7%	23.1%	Including in the activities a discussion about the feedback received by stakeholders
Reusability of the produced knowledge and results of the process	30.8%	7.7%	61.5%	

Lessons learned from the pre-validation concern possible adjustments of the IPDP, mainly related to the duration of the activities planned in the process. Moreover, stakeholders suggested including in the activities a discussion about the feedback received by participants of the different participatory workshops that will be implemented within the HealthyW8 project. The suggested improvements will be applied to the IPDP before its implementation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study described an IPDP that combines DT and UCD approaches for engaging stakeholders in the definition of intervention strategies supported by technological tools for obesity prevention. In particular, DT was employed for co-creating innovative intervention strategies for obesity prevention in the public health sector. At the same time, the UCD method was applied to actively involve stakeholders in the co-designing of technological tools for supporting the implementation of the co-created intervention strategies through personalized recommendations. However, it must be noted that the ability to implement suggested functionalities from the co-creation process was limited by the project's time constraints and the capacity and budget of the technical partners so that priority was given to the enhancement of previously existing components rather than developing new tools from scratch.

The implementation of the IPDP within the HealthyW8 project through stakeholder workshops and field trials will help to evaluate the effectiveness of the methodology at the international level.

Based on the results of a pre-validation, one of the main success points of the IPDP is its capacity to blend the strengths of DT.

Our study is in line with the work of Willmott et al. (2022), which investigates how participatory design can be applied to the development of obesity prevention interventions by incorporating young people directly into the design of treatments. Another study conducted by Jones et al. (2020) applies

a co-design process for developing digital mental health tools, involving children and teenagers to make sure that the tools are in line with their preferences, mental health issues, and technological interaction styles. However, both studies focused on a specific participatory approach either for the development of obesity prevention interventions (Willmott et al., 2022) or for developing digital health tools (Jones et al., 2020). Using a blended design approach, integrating DT and UCD, the HealthyW8 project harnesses the strengths of each, leading to innovative and highly usable obesity intervention strategies and tools.

According to the lessons learned from the pre-validation, the activities planned within the different stages of the IPDP need to be further developed. Specifically, the stakeholders suggested to increase the duration of the activities planned in the process to allow for a more in-depth discussion as well as to include a final discussion about the feedback received by stakeholders.

As future work, after applying the IPDP in the HealthyW8 project, the obtained results will be analyzed to understand the overall success of the IPDP in developing effective intervention strategies and technological tools for obesity prevention.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors of this publication declare there are no competing interests.

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